

References

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Appendix D: Line profile behavior at smaller scales

D.1. Line profile behavior of zoomed-in regions

We address the discrepancies between the fitting results for the 40×40 pc and 20×20 pc regions. **G8_20 (S)**: Located along the southwestern edge of the AGN wind bicone, region G8_20 (S) exhibits a distinct behavior for the CO(6-5) transition compared to region G8_40 (S). While the latter profile is fitted with a single Gaussian, at the smaller scale, it is modeled with a double Gaussian. The minor component is significantly blueshifted from v_{sys} , indicating outflowing gas not captured at the larger scale due to the inclusion of non-outflowing gas outside the AGN wind bicone. **G6_20 (S) & G7_20 (S)**: For these regions, the number of Gaussian components remains unchanged between the two scales; however, the more blueshifted component becomes more prominent in the CO(3-2) line profile at the smaller scale. This likely reflects the exclusion of less blueshifted gas farther from the inner edge of the CND in the smaller regions. **G5_20 (S)**: In the southeastern CND, region G5_20 (S) isolates the most blueshifted outflowing gas within G5_40 (S), resulting in a single Gaussian fit for the CO(2-1) and CO(3-2) line profiles. The stronger average emission within the 20×20 pc region also allows the CO(6-5) line profile to be fitted with a single Gaussian. **G1_20 (N) & G2_20 (N)**: Unlike the southern regions, the 20×20 pc regions in the northern CND, compared to their 40×40 pc counterparts, show smaller or absent wing components. For instance, the CO(3-2) line profile in G2_20 (N) and the CO(6-5) line profile in G1_20 (N) lose their wing components entirely, likely due to the exclusion of gas from the E-knot (see García-Burillo et al. 2019) near the edges of the collimated jet (Galimore et al. 1996, 2004). **G3_20 (N)**: Along the northwestern edge of the AGN wind bicone, the CO(3-2) line profile of region G3_20 (N) is fitted with a redshifted single Gaussian, lacking the slightly blueshifted component observed at the larger scale. The smaller 20×20 pc region likely excludes more gas independent of the outflow that is located farther from the AGN wind bicone.

D.2. Line profile behavior of zoomed-in and shifted regions

For the zoomed-in and shifted regions, results from the new line profiles and their fits further refine the identification of regions contributing to different Gaussian components within the line profiles of the original 40×40 pc regions. **G1_20_DR (N)**: The fitting results for region G1_20_DR (N) are consistent with those of G1_40 (N) across all three CO transitions, featuring a double Gaussian with a broad redshifted wing component. The weight parameters for the wing components in G1_20_DR (N) are larger than those of G1_20 (N) and comparable to G1_40 (N), indicating that G1_20_DR (N), situated near the E-knot (see Sect. 5.3)¹, captures most of the emission from the stronger ionized outflow that dominates G1_40 (N). **G2_20_DR (N)**: For G2_20_DR (N), the CO(2-1) and CO(3-2) line profiles show less outflowing gas compared to G2_40 (N) and G2_20 (N). The CO(2-1) profile is fitted with a single redshifted Gaussian without a broad wing, while the CO(3-2) profile includes an additional Gaussian component centered at v_{sys} . This reduced outflow may result from the geometry of the northern ionized outflow, which is tilted further from the CND plane, causing the wind to intersect molecular gas further from the AGN, near the geometrically thickest part of the CND.

G3_20_L (N): The CO(2-1) line profile of G3_20_L (N) exhibits a more redshifted component and a small blueshifted component, unlike the single Gaussian fits for the same transition in larger regions. With a larger fraction of G3_20_L (N) lying within the AGN wind bicone, more outflowing gas is detected. **G4_20_DR (S)**: Closer to the AGN wind bicone, G4_20_DR (S) contains more outflowing gas than G4_40 (S) and G4_20 (S). The CO(2-1) and CO(3-2) profiles show more prominent blueshifted components, with the CO(3-2) profile reducible to a single Gaussian centered at the velocity of the previous farther blueshifted component. **G5_20_D (S) & G6_20_DR (S)**: For G5_20_D (S) and G6_20_DR (S), further from the CND's inner edge, the CO(3-2) profiles indicate less outflowing gas than previous fits, with smaller weight parameters for the farther blueshifted components. The CO(2-1) emission is too weak for optimal fits, while the CO(6-5) profile in G6_20_DR (S) shows almost no emission. In G5_20_D (S), the CO(6-5) profile is fitted with a less blueshifted single Gaussian, indicating weaker high-velocity outflows. **G7_20_UL (S)**: Near the CND's inner edge, G7_20_UL (S) shows more high-velocity outflowing gas than G7_40 (S) and G7_20 (S). The new CO(2-1) and CO(3-2) profiles feature a farther blueshifted Gaussian component with a larger weight parameter, lacking the less blueshifted wing components seen previously. Together with G5_20_D (S) and G6_20_DR (S), these regions within the southern AGN wind bicone reveal more molecular gas entrained in high-velocity outflows along the inner edge of the CND, contrasting with the line profile behavior in G2_20_DR (N). The southern AGN wind, angled closer to the CND plane, likely interacts with molecular gas at the inner edge and deeper within the CND, driving blueshifted multi-component outflows. In the north, the AGN wind primarily sweeps surface molecular gas, resulting in redshifted broad-wing structures. **G8_20_DL (S)**: Like G4_20_DR (S), G8_20_DL (S) contains more outflowing gas than G8_40 (S) and G8_20 (S), with CO(2-1) and CO(6-5) profiles fitted with a single blueshifted Gaussian rather than multi-component models. The CO(3-2) profile includes a major blueshifted component and a minor component near v_{sys} . **O1_20_DR (E)**: Region O1_20_DR (E) captures outflowing gas extending beyond the AGN wind bicone into the eastern CND. Unlike O1_40 (E) and O1_20 (E), its line profile is fitted with a double Gaussian, including a minor blueshifted component.

Appendix E: Line profiles and their fitting results of zoomed-in 20×20 pc or zoomed-in and shifted regions

¹ Some references to sections, figures, and tables in this standalone appendix document are in the main text, aa53704-25.

Fig. E.1. Zoomed in CO(2-1) transition line profiles of all 20×20 pc regions defined based on the outflow occupying the exact locations on the background plot as their corresponding original 40×40 pc regions assigned in the region definition in Sect. 3.2 (positions of the inset plots only represent the rough locations of the sampled 20×20 pc regions). Region numbers, including their colors, are indicated at the upper left corner of each plot, corresponding to those appearing in the region codes in Table E.1 and are defined in Sect. 5.3. The size of the regions, 20×20 pc, is indicated at the lower left corner of the background plot, and all other symbols are the same in the background plot and line profile diagrams as those in Fig. 8.

Fig. E.3. Zoomed in CO(3-2) transition line profiles of all 20×20 pc regions defined based on the outflow occupying the exact locations on the background plot as their corresponding original 40×40 pc regions assigned in the region definition in Sect. 3.2 (positions of the inset plots only represent the rough locations of the sampled 20×20 pc regions). Region numbers, including their colors, are indicated at the upper left corner of each plot, corresponding to those appearing in the region codes in Table E.1 and are defined in Sect. 5.3. The size of the regions, 20×20 pc, is indicated at the lower left corner of the background plot, and all other symbols are the same in the background plot and line profile diagrams as those in Fig. 9.

Fig. E.4. CO(3-2) transition line profiles of all further zoomed-in and shifted regions defined based on the outflow occupying the exact locations on the background plot as their corresponding original 40×40 pc regions assigned in the region definition in Sect. 3.2 (positions of the inset plots only represent the rough locations of the sampled zoomed-in and shifted regions). Region numbers, including their colors, are indicated at the upper left corner of each plot, corresponding to those appearing in the region codes in Table E.2 and are defined in Sect. 5.3.1. Different definitions of the regions (sizes and their locations within corresponding 40×40 pc regions) are indicated at the upper right corner of each line profile diagram, and all other symbols are the same in the background plot and line profile diagrams as those in Fig. 9.

Fig. E.5. Zoomed in CO(6-5) transition line profiles of all 20×20 pc regions defined based on the outflow occupying the exact locations on the background plot as their corresponding original 40×40 pc regions assigned in the region definition in Sect. 3.2 (positions of the inset plots only represent the rough locations of the sampled 20×20 pc regions). Region numbers, including their colors, are indicated at the upper left corner of each plot, corresponding to those appearing in the region codes in Table E.1 and are defined in Sect. 5.3. The size of the regions, 20×20 pc, is indicated at the lower left corner of the background plot, and all other symbols are the same in the background plot and line profile diagrams as those in Fig. 10.

Fig. E.6. CO(6-5) transition line profiles of all further zoomed-in and shifted regions defined based on the outflow occupying the exact locations on the background plot as their corresponding original 40×40 pc regions assigned in the region definition in Sect. 3.2 (positions of the inset plots only represent the rough locations of the sampled zoomed-in and shifted regions). Region numbers, including their colors, are indicated at the upper left corner of each plot, corresponding to those appearing in the region codes in Table E.2 and are defined in Sect. 5.3.1. Different definitions of the regions (sizes and their locations within corresponding 40×40 pc regions) are indicated at the upper right corner of each line profile diagram, and all other symbols are the same in the background plot and line profile diagrams as those in Fig. 10.

Table E.1. Fitting results of CO line profiles sampled from 20×20 pc regions defined based on the outflow

Transition	Region	#	w_1	w_2	w_3	μ_1	σ_1	μ_2	σ_2	μ_3	σ_3	
CO(2-1)	G1_20 (N)	2	0.79 ± 0.25	0.21 ± 0.24		1149.9 ± 9.1	60.6 ± 3.8	1252 ± 86	80 ± 28			
	G2_20 (N)	2	0.923 ± 0.070	0.077 ± 0.060		1159.3 ± 5.1	50.4 ± 2.3	1259 ± 50	36 ± 10			
	G3_20 (N)	1				1132.3 ± 2.4	65.1 ± 2.1					
	G4_20 (S)	2	0.865 ± 0.053	0.135 ± 0.041		993.4 ± 3.7	43.5 ± 2.1	1077.1 ± 4.8	20.6 ± 3.4			
	G5_20 (S)	1				950.0 ± 1.5	37.8 ± 1.6					
	G6_20 (S)	1				972.0 ± 2.3	54.4 ± 2.4					
	G7_20 (S)	2	0.571 ± 0.062	0.429 ± 0.055		1017.0 ± 2.1	27.5 ± 2.2	991.3 ± 4.6	65.2 ± 3.8			
	G8_20 (S)	3	0.812 ± 0.037	0.109 ± 0.011	0.079 ± 0.028	1098.9 ± 3.6	56.5 ± 2.7	899.9 ± 4.0	36.8 ± 5.1		989.3 ± 5.0	21.9 ± 5.1
	O1_20 (E)	1				1109.1 ± 1.1	51.47 ± 0.78					
	O2_20 (W)	1				1125.5 ± 1.0	46.25 ± 0.76					
CO(3-2)	G1_20 (N)	3	0.78 ± 0.73	0.22 ± 0.73	0.0065 ± 0.0043	1157 ± 19	65.5 ± 9.5	1250 ± 240	85 ± 72	1494 ± 27	23 ± 46	
	G2_20 (N)	1				1172.5 ± 1.3	48.43 ± 0.97					
	G3_20 (N)	1				1136.8 ± 1.3	50.26 ± 0.97					
	G4_20 (S)	2	0.75 ± 0.14	0.25 ± 0.14		988.5 ± 8.8	40.8 ± 3.5	1065 ± 17	34.6 ± 6.5			
	G5_20 (S)	1				947.6 ± 1.5	37.6 ± 1.5					
	G6_20 (S)	2	0.67 ± 0.10	0.33 ± 0.12		954.3 ± 5.9	39.1 ± 4.2	1070 ± 14	50 ± 17			
	G7_20 (S)	2	0.517 ± 0.052	0.483 ± 0.061		994.3 ± 2.2	59.5 ± 2.3	1019.0 ± 2.4	26.3 ± 2.2			
	G8_20 (S)	3	0.768 ± 0.046	0.148 ± 0.038	0.0840 ± 0.0061	1113.7 ± 4.2	49.7 ± 2.2	1006.2 ± 6.9	30.6 ± 5.0		892.9 ± 2.3	28.7 ± 2.7
	O1_20 (E)	1				1115.3 ± 1.1	54.51 ± 0.71					
	O2_20 (W)	1				1123.22 ± 0.94	48.75 ± 0.61					
CO(6-5)	G1_20 (N)	1				1172.5 ± 1.6	76.6 ± 1.2					
	G2_20 (N)	1				1160.1 ± 1.2	43.49 ± 0.94					
	G3_20 (N)	1				1165.4 ± 7.6	45 ± 18					
	G4_20 (S)	1				999.5 ± 3.0	45.7 ± 4.5					
	G5_20 (S)	1				949 ± 11	40 ± 24					
	G7_20 (S)	1				1008.8 ± 1.2	30.3 ± 1.2					
	O8_20 (S)	2	0.65 ± 0.11	0.35 ± 0.16		1093.2 ± 8.3	56.5 ± 9.7	911 ± 23	67 ± 36			
	O1_20 (E)	1				1118.6 ± 1.4	49.9 ± 1.3					
	O2_20 (W)	1				1135.1 ± 1.2	46.21 ± 0.94					

Notes. Fitting results of CO(2-1), CO(3-2), and CO(6-5) line profiles sampled from the zoomed-in 20×20 pc regions defined based on the outflow, centered at the coordinates provided in Table 2. The schematics of the table are the same as Table C.1.

Table E.2. Fitting results of CO line profiles sampled from zoomed-in and shifted 20×20 pc regions defined based on the outflow

Transition	Region	#	w_1	w_2	w_3	μ_1	σ_1	μ_2	σ_2	μ_3	σ_3
CO(2-1)	G1_20_DR (N)	2	0.663 ± 0.099	0.337 ± 0.099		1162.7 ± 3.8	58.7 ± 4.0	1244 ± 21	93.0 ± 5.4		
	G2_20_DR (N)	1				1165.4 ± 1.9	64.2 ± 1.9				
	G3_20_L (N)	3	0.505 ± 0.094	0.442 ± 0.090	0.053 ± 0.016	1116.4 ± 4.7	26.7 ± 3.1	1189.2 ± 8.8	34.9 ± 4.3	1012.3 ± 5.3	30 ± 11
	G4_20_DR (S)	2	0.9 ± 1.9	~ 0.1		986.7 ± 1.7	39.4 ± 1.6	~ 1085	~ 5		
	G5_20_D (S)	1				1075 ± 81	160 ± 76				
CO(3-2)	G6_20_DR (S)	1				1023.7 ± 6.9	106 ± 15				
	G7_20_UL (S)	2	0.52 ± 0.12	0.48 ± 0.12		938 ± 13	46.8 ± 7.1	1015.8 ± 4.2	27.0 ± 3.7		
	G8_20_DL (S)	1			“–”	1036.4 ± 1.7	60.8 ± 1.5				
	O1_20_DR (E)	3	0.78 ± 0.24	0.22 ± 0.21		1105 ± 13	44 ± 11	1025 ± 21	34.0 ± 6.9	1238 ± 22	34 ± 30
	G1_20_DR (N)	2	0.59 ± 0.13	0.41 ± 0.13		1166.6 ± 4.8	61.3 ± 5.3	1234 ± 19	91.7 ± 4.0		
	G2_20_DR (N)	2	0.59 ± 0.12	0.41 ± 0.11		1200.0 ± 8.6	35.8 ± 3.9	1125.2 ± 8.2	28.5 ± 4.3		
	G3_20_L (N)	1				1142.1 ± 1.1	51.07 ± 0.83				
	G4_20_DR (S)	1				989.1 ± 1.1	40.27 ± 0.80				
CO(6-5)	G5_20_D (S)	3	0.516 ± 0.058	0.484 ± 0.030	“–”	1065.4 ± 1.9	22.3 ± 1.9	951.3 ± 2.8	43.4 ± 3.8	1182.5 ± 7.9	53 ± 21
	G6_20_DR (S)	2	0.740 ± 0.037	0.260 ± 0.024		1075.8 ± 1.7	31.1 ± 1.4	960.3 ± 3.6	38.2 ± 4.6		
	G7_20_UL (S)	2	0.524 ± 0.093	0.476 ± 0.094		929.4 ± 8.8	41.0 ± 4.9	1019.7 ± 6.8	33.0 ± 4.0	904 ± 10	30 ± 10
	G8_20_DL (S)	3	0.521 ± 0.098	0.423 ± 0.087	0.056 ± 0.021	1006.6 ± 5.7	33.2 ± 5.0	1096.4 ± 9.8	39.2 ± 4.8		
	O1_20_DR (E)	2	0.810 ± 0.089	0.190 ± 0.084		1105.3 ± 6.8	46.4 ± 3.1	1021.8 ± 9.7	30.8 ± 4.0		
	G2_20_DR (N)	2	0.83 ± 0.38	0.17 ± 0.38		1175 ± 12	62.4 ± 5.6	1280 ± 180	85 ± 70		
	G3_20_L (N)	1				1146 ± 13	32 ± 21				
	G4_20_DR (S)	1	“+”	“–”		1158 ± 11	51.8 ± 8.5	1055 ± 21	25 ± 23		
CO(6-5)	G5_20_D (S)	1				983.4 ± 7.2	52 ± 21				
	G7_20_UL (S)	1				1078.6 ± 5.8	35 ± 15				
	G8_20_DL (S)	1				1027 ± 49	100 ± 55				
	G8_20_DL (S)	1				1022.1 ± 6.4	67 ± 11				
	O1_20_DR (E)	1				1083.4 ± 2.3	56.5 ± 2.4				

Notes. Fitting results of CO(2-1), CO(3-2), and CO(6-5) line profiles sampled from the zoomed-in and shifted 20×20 pc regions defined based on outflow. The definition of the zoom and shift for each region is stated in Sect. 5.3.1. The “+” and “–” signs indicate Gaussian components of the emission and absorption, respectively. Only the positive Gaussian components are considered for the weight calculation. The “~” sign is used when the fitting result contains a large error bar (not provided in the table). The rest of the schematics is the same as Table C.1.

**Appendix F: LTE analysis results of zoomed-in
20 × 20 pc or zoomed-in and shifted regions**

Fig. F.1. Rotational diagrams of all zoomed-in 20×20 regions defined based on the outflow occupying the same locations on the background plot as their corresponding original 40×40 pc regions assigned in the region definition in Sect. 3.2 (positions of the inset plots only represent the rough locations of the sampled 20×20 pc regions). Region numbers, including their colors, are indicated at the lower left corner of each diagram, corresponding to those appearing in the region codes in Table F.1 and are defined in Sect. 5.3. The sampled region size is indicated in the lower-left corner. All the other symbols and markers of the background plot are the same as Fig. 5.

Fig. F.2. Rotational diagrams of all zoomed-in and shifted regions defined based on the outflow occupying the same locations on the background plot as their corresponding original $40 \times 40 \text{ pc}$ regions assigned in the region definition in Sect. 3.2 (positions of the inset plots only represent the rough locations of the sampled zoomed-in and shifted regions). Region numbers, including their colors, are indicated at the lower left corner of each diagram, corresponding to those appearing in the region codes in Table F.2 and are defined in Sect. 5.3.1. The sampled region definitions are indicated at the upper-right corners of all rotational diagrams. All the other symbols and markers of the background plot are the same as Fig. 5.

Table F.1. Rotational temperatures and total CO column densities from 20×20 pc regions defined based on outflow

Region	Rotational Temperature (T_{rot})	CO(2-1)	CO(3-2)	CO(6-5)
G1_20 (N)	58.6 ± 4.6	69.4 ± 9.2	57.3 ± 7.9	64 ± 13
G2_20 (N)	46.1 ± 2.9	22.6 ± 2.8	19.3 ± 2.5	21.4 ± 4.3
G3_20 (N)	34.7 ± 1.8	8.7 ± 1.1	8.8 ± 1.2	8.8 ± 1.9
G4_20 (S)	31.8 ± 1.4	12.5 ± 1.5	10.5 ± 1.3	11.8 ± 2.4
G5_20 (S)	41.0 ± 2.6	3.08 ± 0.40	2.56 ± 0.35	2.89 ± 0.66
G6_20 (S)	32.1 ± 1.9	2.69 ± 0.35	2.50 ± 0.35	2.64 ± 0.71
G7_20 (S)	35.8 ± 1.7	15.1 ± 1.8	11.4 ± 1.4	13.6 ± 2.6
G8_20 (S)	32.3 ± 1.5	16.4 ± 2.0	13.5 ± 1.7	15.4 ± 3.2
O1_20 (E)	38.6 ± 2.0	26.3 ± 3.1	22.9 ± 2.9	25.1 ± 4.9
O2_20 (W)	44.3 ± 2.7	24.6 ± 3.1	21.3 ± 2.8	23.3 ± 4.7

Notes. LTE rotational temperatures (T_{rot}) and total CO column densities (N) from the zoomed-in 20×20 pc regions defined based on outflow in units of K and 10^{17} cm^{-2} respectively. The total CO column density calculated from each CO transition is indicated by the name of each transition in the header. The location of each region within the CND is also provided in brackets (e.g., “N” stands for the northern CND).

Table F.2. Rotational temperatures and total CO column densities from zoomed-in and shifted 20×20 pc regions defined based on outflow

Region	Rotational Temperature (T_{rot})	CO(2-1)	CO(3-2)	CO(6-5)
G1_20_DR (N)	59.4 ± 4.8	75.2 ± 10.0	64.0 ± 8.8	71 ± 15
G2_20_DR (N)	48.9 ± 4.2	11.5 ± 1.8	8.0 ± 1.3	10.2 ± 2.7
G3_20_L (N)	39.6 ± 2.2	11.1 ± 1.4	11.1 ± 1.4	11.1 ± 2.3
G4_20_DR (S)	29.7 ± 1.3	7.21 ± 0.87	6.32 ± 0.81	6.9 ± 1.5
G5_20_D (S)	53.3 ± 4.2	1.99 ± 0.27	1.67 ± 0.23	1.86 ± 0.41
G6_20_DR (S)	25.0 ± 1.0	2.33 ± 0.29	3.41 ± 0.44	2.60 ± 0.62
G7_20_UL (S)	39.1 ± 2.3	7.52 ± 0.99	5.43 ± 0.75	6.7 ± 1.5
G8_20_DL (S)	36.9 ± 2.0	10.7 ± 1.4	8.7 ± 1.2	9.9 ± 2.1
O1_20_DR (E)	34.9 ± 1.8	19.2 ± 2.4	15.7 ± 2.0	17.8 ± 3.8

Notes. LTE rotational temperatures (T_{rot}) and total CO column densities (N) from the further zoomed-in or shifted regions defined based on outflow in units of K and 10^{17} cm^{-2} respectively. The total CO column density calculated from each CO transition is indicated by the name of each transition in the header. The location of each region within the CND is also provided in brackets (e.g., “N” stands for the northern CND).

Fig. F.3. Summary of rotational temperatures for all zoomed-in 20×20 pc (left panel) or zoomed-in and shifted (right panel) regions sampled around the CND defined based on the outflow in Sect. 5.3. The x-axis marks the region labels along with their locations around the CND (in brackets), while the y-axis indicates the rotational temperatures in the unit of K. The region code (along the x-axis) and color (the color of the data points) of each region match those in Table F.1 and are defined in Sect. 5.3. All other symbols and markers are the same as in Fig. 7.

Fig. F.4. Total CO column densities (N) independently calculated from three CO transitions for all zoomed-in 20×20 pc (*left panel*) or all zoomed-in and shifted (*right panel*) regions selected based on the outflow. The x-axis marks the region labels along with their locations around the CND (in brackets), while the y-axis indicates the total CO column densities in the unit of cm^{-2} . The region code (along the x-axis) and color (the color of the data points) of each region match those in Table F.1 and are defined in Sect. 5.3. All other symbols and markers are the same as Fig. 6.

Appendix G: Velocity-integrated Maps of Outflowing CO Gas

Fig. G.1. Velocity-integrated map of outflowing CO(2-1) gas in units of K km s^{-1} . The color ranges from the minimum to the maximum value in the logarithmic scale, and the contour covers the same extent with levels 3σ , 5σ , 10σ , 20σ , 30σ , 40σ , 60σ , 80σ , 100σ , and 130σ , where $1\sigma = 50.6 \text{ K km s}^{-1}$. All other symbols and markers are the same as in Fig. 1.

Fig. G.2. The same as Fig. G.1 but for the CO(3-2) transition. The contours cover the same extent as the color bar with levels 3σ , 5σ , 10σ , 20σ , 40σ , 60σ , 100σ , 140σ , and 185σ , where $1\sigma = 49.5 \text{ K km s}^{-1}$.

Fig. G.3. The same as Fig. G.1 but for the CO(6-5) transition. The contours cover the same extent as the color bar with levels 3σ , 5σ , 10σ , 15σ , 20σ , 40σ , 60σ , 80σ , and 100σ , where $1\sigma = 99.9 \text{ K km s}^{-1}$.